

A TEXTILE-BASED VIABLE COMPOSITE STENT FOR VASCULAR APPLICATION

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1 Introduction

The patency rates of small caliber vessels (<Ø 6mm) after stent implantation remain unsatisfactory [1]. The concept of the BioStent is to avoid in-stent restenosis through a vitalized stent surface. The key element of the concept is the combination of conventional stent technology with a Tissue Engineering approach. This vitalized composite structure is able to eliminate two major reasons of restenosis. On the one hand, the atherosclerotic vessel section is totally excluded from the blood stream and secondly a totally intact and functional endothelial cell layer is available on the lumen side of the stent providing optimum hemocompatibility. The proof of concept of this textile-based composite structure was successfully carried out and promising results were found [2]. It could be shown that a warp knitted tubular structure as textile stent structure is highly appropriate for the BioStent concept.

The aim of the present study was to analyze the influence of different warp knitting process parameters on the mechanical properties of the stent structure. The impact of the components textile and fibrin (cell carrier) on the mechanical properties such as radial force and deformation resistance are equally investigated. This approach examining the correlation of parameters and properties can be transferred to the development of other textile-based composite implant structures.

2 Materials and Methods

2.1 The BioStent Production Process

The production of the BioStent has previously been described [1]. The vitalized stent consists of a self-expanding, warp knitted Nitinol structure which is embedded into a cell-fibrin matrix. An injection moulding process was established to cover the stent

structure with a smooth muscle cell and fibrinogen suspension. The suspension polymerizes within 45 minutes after injection. The composite structure is then placed in a bioreactor system for cultivation. In a further step, endothelial cells are added to the inner surface of the tubular structure in order to most closely mimic the native vessel.

2.2 The textile stent structure

Four different stent configurations were produced. The pattern and the take up speed were varied (see table 1). A superelastic nitinol wire (NiTi Nr.1SE; Fort Wayne Metals, Indiana, USA) with a thickness of 76 µm was used in all stents. The structures were produced on a double-bar raschel warp knitting machine (Karl Meyer Textilmaschinenfabrik GmbH, Obertshausen, Germany). The fabrics were thermosetted at 500 °C for 15 minutes on a metal core (Ø 6mm).

2.3 Mechanical testing

Radial force, local compression and deformation resistance were analyzed for all stent structures. All tests were carried out following DIN EN ISO 25539-2. Samples were mounted in a uniaxial Zwick tensile testing machine. Special clamps or testing devices were manufactured. For radial force measurements the samples were placed in between two "V"-clamps. Force and displacement were recorded throughout tests. The test consisted of measuring the force applied by the stent to the upper V-clamp during deployment. The local compression indicates the resistance that a stent opposes to a locally applied force. A stamp of Ø 4 mm was used. The stent was locally compressed by the stamp down to 2 mm and released. Force and displacement of the stamp were measured. For deformation resistance

the stent was compressed using two metal plates in order to apply a uniform load over the stent length. The stent was compromised to 1 mm. The upper plate was then returned to its starting position. Force and displacement were again measured.

3 Results

Different warp knitted stent structures were produced (see figure 1) and mechanically characterized. The different parameter sets were compared for each test. The results obtained for the radial force of the different stents is shown in figure 2. Values from literature for similar tests on commercially available stents [3] were compared and analyzed with the data gained from testing. Considering all test data achieved, a clear correlation between the process parameters and mechanical properties of the stent was found. A higher take up speed and underlap both result in increased mechanical properties. Parameter set ‘Trikot 10’ showed the best results for all tests carried out.

For the long-term success of the implant the behavior not just of the textile but of the composite is crucial. Mechanical testing was repeated for the textile-fibrin composite. Due to the time and cost intensive cell culturing, it was decided to evaluate the textile-fibrin construct without cells in a first step. No significant differences could be determined between textile and textile-fibrin structure. This supports the expectation that the textile structure is mainly responsible for the mechanical properties of the composite. However the tests will need to be repeated in combination with the cellular component(s) as these may have a major impact on the construct’s mechanical properties. The results gained will be used to improve the textile structure to increase the mechanical properties of the BioStent.

Table 1: Sets of investigated warp knitting parameters

Parameter Set Term	Pattern	Take up speed [stitches/cm]
Trikot 7	1x1, 1x1	7
Trikot 10	1x1, 1x1	10
Charmeuse 5	1x1, 2x1	5
Charmeuse 7	1x1, 2x1	7

Fig. 1: Warp knitted stent structures: (A) 1x1, 2x1 – 5 stitches/cm, (B) 1x1,2x1 – 7 stitches/cm, (C) 1x1, 1x1 – 7 stitches/cm, (D) 1x1, 1x1 – 10 stitches/cm

Fig. 2: Radial forces obtained for the analyzed stent geometries at different diameters

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